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OVERVIEW AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECT HDFC MUTUAL FUNDS: EQUITY FUND AND GROWTH FUND – GROWTH OPTION

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ABSTRACT

The two mutual funds (i) Equity (G) and Growth (G) of the fund House, HDFC are reviewed in a detailed fashion with a brief introduction of the fund house itself. The funds are then statistically evaluated by correlation with the benchmark, S&P CNX Nifty, standard deviation, Sharpe’s Index, Treynor’s Ratio, Jensen’s alpha, Fama’s Measure and M². An analytical review of the funds is incorporated.

KEYWORDS: *HDFC Funds, Equity (G) and Growth(G), Review and Statistical Evaluation.*

INTRODUCTION

“HDFC Asset Management Company Ltd (AMC) was incorporated under the Companies Act, 1956, on December 10, 1999, and was approved to act as an Asset Management Company for the HDFC Mutual Fund by SEBI vide its letter dated July 3, 2000.

Particulars	Paid up equity capital (%)
Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited	59.98
Standard Life Investments Limited	39.99
Other Shareholders (shares issued on exercise of Stock Options)	0.03

Zurich Insurance Company (ZIC), the Sponsor of Zurich India Mutual Fund, following a review of its overall strategy, had decided to divest its Asset Management business in India. The AMC had entered into an agreement with ZIC to acquire the said business, subject to necessary regulatory approvals. On obtaining the regulatory approvals, the following Schemes of Zurich India Mutual Fund have migrated to HDFC Mutual Fund on June 19, 2003. These Schemes have been renamed. The AMC is also providing portfolio management / advisory services and such activities are not in conflict with the activities of the Mutual Fund. The AMC has renewed its registration from SEBI vide Registration No. - PM / INP000000506 dated December 21, 2009 to act as a Portfolio Manager under the SEBI (Portfolio Managers) Regulations, 1993. The Certificate of Registration is valid from January 1, 2010 to December 31, 2012.

In terms of the Investment Management Agreement, the Trustee has appointed the HDFC Asset Management Company Limited to manage the Mutual Fund. The paid up capital of the AMC is Rs. 25.161 crore. HDFC was incorporated in 1977 as the first specialised Mortgage Company in India. HDFC provides financial assistance to individuals, corporates and developers for the purchase or construction of residential housing. It also provides property related services (e.g. property identification, sales services and valuation), training and consultancy. Of these activities, housing finance remains the dominant activity.

To invest funds in debt markets or in equity from a pool of money of several people is called Mutual Fund. The HDFC bank offers HDFC Mutual Fund which is one of the known Indian Mutual Funds. The Debt funds, balanced funds or Equity funds come under Mutual Funds. There are parameters which are quantitative based on which the funds are selected. The volatility, risk adjustment returns, FAMA model, rolling return, qualitative analysis, fund performance are some of the important parameters based on which the funds are selected”.

HDFC MUTUAL FUND ADVANTAGES

There are many advantages in investing HDFC mutual funds.

- **AFFORDABILITY** – The HDFC mutual funds are available in smaller units which make it more affordable.
- **FLEXIBILITY** – The HDFC mutual fund offers systematic withdrawal plans, dividend reinvestment, systematic investment plans which give more flexibility.
- **LIQUIDITY** – The HDFC mutual fund offers open ended schemes in which you can withdraw the money at any point of time.
- **PROFESSIONAL MANAGEMENT** – Based on extensive research and experience the expert fund managers analyze the options in HDFC mutual funds.
- **DIVERSIFICATION** – The risk factor is low in HDFC mutual funds as the investment is done across different stocks and industries.

- **LOW COSTS** – The custodial fee, brokerage charges are low for HDFC mutual funds.
- **POTENTIAL RETURN** – The HDFC mutual fund managers have access to statistics and information from leading analysts and economists around the world. Because of this, the investors of HDFC mutual funds gain potential returns.
- **REGULATED FOR INVESTOR PROTECTION** – The HDFC mutual fund sector is regulated to protect the interests of investors.

Some of the mutual funds floated by the bank are:

- **HDFC MID: CAP OPPORTUNITIES FUND:** Closed end fund which invests in small as well as mid cap stocks.
- **HDFC INFRASTRUCTURE FUND:** Closed end equity mutual fund which invests in stocks of the infrastructure companies.
- **HDFC LONG TERM EQUITY FUND:** Closed end equity mutual fund and has a maturity period of 5 years. This fund has diversified stocks for risk minimization.
- **HDFC INDEX FUND: Nifty Plan:** This is an index fund and tracks nifty. The scheme is open ended and the expense ratio is 1%.
- **HDFC INDEX FUND: Sensex Plus Plan:** 80-90% of the asset in this fund is invested in Sensex stocks and the rest is invested outside Sensex.
- **HDFC INDEX FUND: Sensex Plan:** Passively tracks the Sensex.
- **HDFC EQUITY FUND:** Open ended fund where the investments are made companies which are expected to outperform their peers.
- **HDFC BALANCED FUND:** It is a balanced open-ended fund where investments are made in equity and debt.
- **HDFC CORE AND SATELLITE FUND:** Open-ended fund investing in stocks which are performing below the true value.
- **HDFC TOP 200 FUND:** This fund invests in the equities and instruments linked with equity but are drawn from the companies listed in the BSE 200 Index.
- **HDFC GROWTH FUND:** Open-ended fund and invests primarily in equities

No. of schemes	110
No. of schemes including options	303
Equity Schemes	31
Debt Schemes	246
Short term debt Schemes	13
Equity & Debt	6
Money Market	0
Gilt Fund	4
Corpus under management as on Mar 31, 2012	₹.86102.96 Crs

The present work is aimed at studying the two schemes offered by the fund family, HDFC, (i) Equity Fund (G) and Growth Fund (G). Number of schemes selected was kept to a bare minimum with a view to make the study explicable and comprehensive including the minutest of details. Further, the performance of these funds are evaluated almost from the times of inception to the present time by statistical evaluation.

HDFC EQUITY FUND (GROWTH OPTION)

OBJECTIVES: Aims at providing capital appreciation through investments predominantly in equity oriented securities

INVESTMENT PATTERN

TABLE.1. THE ASSET ALLOCATION UNDER THE SCHEME

Asset Type	Portfolio %	Risk Profile
Equities and Equity Related Instruments	80 – 100	Medium High
Debt & Money Market Instruments	0 - 20	Low Medium

Investment in Securitised debt, if undertaken, would not exceed 20% of the net assets of the scheme.

The Scheme may also invest up to 25% of net assets of the Scheme in derivatives such as Futures & Options and such other derivative instruments as may be introduced from time to time for the purpose of hedging and portfolio balancing and other uses as may be permitted under the Regulations.

The Scheme may also invest a part of its corpus, not exceeding 40% of its net assets, in overseas markets in Global Depository Receipts (GDRs), ADRs, overseas equity, bonds and mutual funds and such other instruments as may be allowed under the Regulations from time to time. Also refer to the Section on Policy on off-shore Investments by the Scheme(s). Subject to the Regulations and the applicable guidelines, the Scheme may, engage in Stock Lending activities. If the investment in equities and related instruments falls below 70% of the

portfolio of the Scheme at any point in time, it would try to review and rebalance the composition. Notwithstanding anything stated above, subject to the regulations, the asset allocation pattern indicated above may change from time to time, keeping in view market conditions, market opportunities, applicable regulations and political and economic factors. It may be clearly understood that the percentages stated above are only indicative and are not absolute and that they can vary substantially depending upon the perception of the AMC, the intention being at all times to seek to protect the NAV of the scheme. Such changes will be for short term and defensive considerations. Provided further and subject to the above, any change in the asset allocation affecting the investment profile of the Scheme and amounting to a change in the Fundamental Attributes of the Scheme shall be effected in accordance with sub-regulation (15A) of regulation 18 of SEBI regulations.

INVESTMENT STRATEGY

In order to provide long term capital appreciation, the Scheme will invest predominantly in growth companies. Companies selected under this portfolio would as far as practicable consist of medium to large sized companies which:

- enjoy distinct competitive advantages, and
- have superior financial strengths.

The aim will be to build a portfolio, which represents a cross-section of the strong growth companies in the prevailing market. In order to reduce the risk of volatility, the Scheme will diversify across major industries and economic sectors

HDFC GROWTH FUND (GROWTH OPTION)

INVESTMENT OBJECTIVE: The primary investment objective of the Scheme is to generate long term capital appreciation from a portfolio that is invested predominantly in equity and equity related instruments.

INVESTMENT PATTERN

The corpus of the Scheme will be invested primarily in equity and equity related instruments. The Scheme may invest a part of its corpus in debt and money market instruments, in order to manage its liquidity requirements from time to time, and under certain circumstances, to protect the interests of the Unit holders.

TABLE.2. THE ASSET ALLOCATION UNDER THE SCHEME

Type of Instruments	Normal Allocation (% of Net Assets)	Normal Deviation (% of Normal Allocation)	Risk Profile
Equity & Equity related instruments	80- 20	0	Medium to High
Debt Securities, Money	0 – 20	0	Low to Medium

Pending deployment of funds of the Scheme in securities in terms of the investment objective of the Scheme, the AMC may invest the funds of the Scheme in short term deposits of scheduled commercial banks.

INVESTMENT APPROACH

The investment approach will be based on a set of well established but flexible principles that emphasize the concept of sustainable economic earnings and cash return on investment as the means of valuation of companies.

The twin principles that serve as the foundation for this investment approach:

1. Focus on the long term: There is substantive empirical evidence to suggest that equities provide the maximum risk adjusted returns over the long term. In an attempt to take full advantage of this phenomenon, investments would be made with a long term perspective
2. Investments confer proportionate ownership. The approach to valuing a company is similar to making an investment in a business. Therefore, there is a need to have a comprehensive understanding of how the business operates. The key issues to focus on are growth opportunities, sustainable competitive advantage, industry structure, margins and quality of the management and to maintain a margin of safety.

The benchmark for determining relative attractiveness of stocks would be the intrinsic value of the business. The Investment Manager would endeavor to purchase stocks that represent a discount to this value, in an effort to preserve capital and generate superior growth:

1. Maintain a balanced outlook on the market. The investment portfolio would be regularly monitored to understand the impact of changes in business and economic trend as well as investor sentiment. While short-term market volatility would affect valuations of the portfolio, this is not expected to influence the decision to own fundamentally strong companies
2. Disciplined approach to selling The decision to sell a holding would be based on either the anticipated price appreciation being achieved or being no longer possible due to a change in fundamental factors affecting the company or the market in which it competes, or due to the availability of an alternative that, in the view of the Investment Manager, offers superior returns.

In order to implement the investment approach effectively, it would be important to periodically meet the management face to face. This would provide an understanding of their broad vision and commitment to the long-term business objectives. These meetings would also be useful in assessing key determinants of management quality such as orientation to minority shareholders, ability to cope with adversity and approach to allocating surplus cash flows. Discussion with management would also enable benchmarking actual performance against stated commitments.

The Scheme may invest in:

3. listed / unlisted and/or rated / unrated debt or money market securities subject to limits indicated in the investment pattern. Investment in unrated debt securities will be made after obtaining the prior approval of the Board of the AMC and Trustees as per the SEBI Regulations.

4. listed / unlisted and / or rated / unrated debt or money market securities subject to limits indicated in the investment pattern. Pursuant to SEBI Circular No. MFD/ CIR/9/120/2000 dated November 24, 2000, the AMC may constitute committee(s) to approve proposals for investments in unrated debt instruments. The AMC Board and the Trustee shall approve the detailed parameters for such investments. The details of such investments would be communicated by the AMC to the Trustee in their periodical reports. It would also be clearly mentioned in the reports, how the parameters have been complied with. However, in case any unrated debt security does not fall under the parameters, the prior approval of Board of AMC and Trustee shall be sought in order to implement the investment approach effectively, it would be important to periodically meet the management face to face. This would provide an understanding of their broad vision and commitment to the long-term business objectives. These meetings would also be useful in assessing key determinants of management quality such as orientation to minority shareholders, ability to cope with adversity and approach to allocating surplus cash flows. Discussion with management would also enable benchmarking actual performance against stated commitments.

In summary, the Investment Strategy is expected to be a function of extensive research and based on data and reasoning, rather than current fashion and emotion. The objective will be to identify "businesses with superior growth prospects and good management, at a reasonable price".

KEY FEATURES OF THE FUNDS

	Equity Plan (G)	Growth Plan (G)
Current Stats & Profile		
Fund Category	Equity: Multi Cap	Equity: Large & Mid Cap
Type	Open End	Open End
Launch Date	December 1994	August 2000
Latest NAV	253.882 (07/09/12)	85.194 (07/09/12)
52-Week High	272 (21/02/12)	88.489 (21/02/12)
52-Week Low	215.059 (20/12/11)	72.53 (20/12/11)
Risk Grade	Average	Below Average
Return Grade	Above Average	Above Average
Net Assets (Cr)	₹ 9,718.17 (30/06/12)	₹ 1,189.22 (30/06/12)
Benchmark	S&P CNX 500	Sensex
*Quarterly Average		
Entry load	Nil	Nil
Exit load	1% If redeemed within 1 year	1% If redeemed within 1 year
Investment (Min.)	₹ .5000	₹ .5000
NAV Comparison : Fund Vs S&P CNX Nifty		

FIG. I NAV COMPARISON - HDFC EQUITY (G) VS S&P CNX NIFTY

FIG. II NAV COMPARISON - HDFC GROWTH VS S&P CNX NIFTY

FUND STYLE

Investment Style			Capitalisation
Growth	Blend	Value	
			Large
			Medium
			Small

FIG. III. FUND STYLE

Investment Style			Capitalisation
Growth	Blend	Value	
			Large
			Medium
			Small

FIG. IV. FUND STYLE

Relative Performance (Fund vs Category Average)

FIG.V. RELATIVE PERFORMANCE (FUND VS CATEGORY)

FIG.VI. RELATIVE PERFORMANCE (FUND VS CATEGORY)

Portfolio Characteristics As on 31/08/12 (Average Mkt Cap (□. Cr) 38,953.56)

FIG. VII. PORTFOLIO CHARACTERISTICS

FIGURE VIII. ASSET ALLOCATION

FIG. IX. PORTFOLIO CHARACTERISTICS

FIG. X. ASSET ALLOCATION (31.8.2012)

FIG. XI. PORTFOLIO CONCENTRATION

FIG. XII. TOP HOLDINGS (% NET ASSETS)

FIG. XIII. PORTFOLIO CONCENTRATION

FIG. XIV. TOP HOLDINGS (% NET ASSETS)

FIG. XV. SECTOR WEIGHTAGE

FIG. XVI. TRAILING RETURNS

FIG. XVII. SECTOR WEIGHTAGE

FIG. XVIII. TRAIL IN G RETURNS

Annual Returns	Equity Fund					Growth Fund				
	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007
Fund Return	-26.72	29.22	105.5	-49.68	53.61	-21.24	27.71	75.26	-48.31	66.43
Rank(Category)	32/4	3/59	4/46	16/59	7/48	9/44	7/59	30/46	8/40	14/34
Average	-24.54	18.69	90.74	-55.18	60.2	-23.33	16.9	78.64	-52.01	53.74
Sensex	-24.65	17.43	81.03	-52.45	47.15	-24.64	17.43	81.03	-52.45	47.15
S&P CNX Nifty	-24.67	17.95	75.76	-51.79	54.77	-24.62	17.95	75.76	-51.79	54.77

Performance (Best & Worst)	Best Period	Worst period	Best period	Worst period
Month	35.86 (28/04/2009 28/05/2009)	-31.58 (26/09/2008 27/10/2008)	30.48 (28/4/2009 28/5/2009)	-30.77 (26/09/2008 27/10/2008)
Quarter	95.14 (09/03/2009 10/6/2009)	-40.02 (2/09/2008 2/12/2008)	75.71 (9/3/2009 10/6/2009)	-35.54 (2/9/2008 2/12/2008)
Year	179.39 (20/10/1998 20/10/1999)	-52.70 (3/12/2007 2/12/2008)	144.95 (23/4/2003 22/4/2004)	-51.22 (14/01/2008 13/01/2009)

METHODOLOGY

With the review of the selected schemes presented above, the analysis of the performance is taken up. The period of study included from the very early days of the funds, starting with the financial year 2002-2003 to the financial year 2011-12. The NAV values of the selected schemes were compiled on monthly basis and compounded to annual returns. (R_p). Similarly the annual returns of the market index, S&P CNX Nifty (R_M) were also obtained. The risk free index (R_F) was taken as the Savings Bank Account Interest Rate offered by State Bank of India, which is 4% for the years 2002 and 2012 and 3.2% for the rest of the years, corresponding to 0.330 and 0.292% respectively.

The statistical evaluation parameters, correlation, standard deviation (σ), Treynor's Index (T_f), Sharpe's Index (S_t), Jensen's Alpha (α_j), Fama's Measure (F_p) and M^2 Measure were computed and the funds were appraised from these observations

METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The NAV values used in the study are obtained from AMFI's website, which in turn is supplied by the members. Members in turn have not followed any uniform rule in its computation due to the flexibilities offered under SEBI regulations.

- Initially all mutual fund schemes were directly linked to stock market. In the recent 2 years numerous schemes which are independent of stock market (debt & money market funds) are introduced and such schemes' returns need not have correlation with index and the index is not adjusted for dividends.
- Banks are free to accept deposits at any interest within the ceilings fixed by Reserve Bank of India and interest rates can vary from client to client. Hence, there can be an inaccuracy in the risk-free rates.
- The analysis is not free from the limitations of non-identical time periods and unequal sample observations.
- The benchmark index selected for the study differs with the index enshrined for the schemes and the study is pointed towards open ended growth funds.
- The study excludes the effect of entry and exit loads of the mutual funds.

OBSERVATIONS AND FINDINGS

The R_p values and the corresponding R_M values and the σ values are included in Table.1. for comparison and correlation. Table.2. depicts the statistical evaluation parameters.

TABLE.1. PORTFOLIO RETURN, MARKET RETURN, AND CORRELATION COEFFICIENT OF THE SELECTED SCHEMES

Fund Year	R_p				R_M	
	Equity		Growth		S&P Nifty	CNX
	R_p	σ	R_p	Σ	R_M	
2011-12	-0.0060	0.0069	-0.0300	0.0579	-0.0120	
2010-11	0.0086	0.0477	0.8300	0.0459	0.0058	
2009-10	4.7760	0.0828	4.0000	0.0805	0.0047	
2008-09	-3.2543	0.1197	-3.6000	0.1012	-0.0383	
2007-08	1.6988	0.0772	3.2000	0.0788	0.0179	
2006-07	0.1986	0.0623	0.2670	0.0642	0.0100	
2005-06	4.5597	0.0524	-3.2000	0.1250	0.0439	
2004-05	1.0254	0.0667	0.0175	0.0653	0.0116	
2003-04	6.9000	0.0718	5.5955	0.0684	0.0512	
2002-03	-2.4812	0.2003	-1.0189	0.0452	-0.011	
$Corr_{(R_p, R_M)}$	0.9616		0.6104			

TABLE.2. STATISTICAL EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Fund	Year	S_t	T_f	α_I	F_P	M^2
HDFC – Equity fund (G)	2011-12	-4.87	-0.3771	-0.0313	-0.3012	1.3250
	2010-11	-5.94	-0.4465	-0.0905	-0.0590	0.0109
	2009-10	2.24	5.9846	-0.0981	-0.0422	1.7873
	2008-09	-2.60	-3.7378	-3.5150	0.3024	-2.2341
	2007-08	18.20	1.7671	1.6300	1.6402	1.8206
	2006-07	-1.50	-0.1070	0.0640	10.5588	0.8957
	2005-06	8.37	6.2305	3.5827	4.7608	1.8296
	2004-05	10.98	0.9717	-0.0214	6.8720	1.7673
	2003-04	2.31	9.0225	0.8756	0.9746	1.6440
	2002-03	-4.03	-0.3135	0.2535	-2.2681	0.1718
	Overall	2.31	1.8995	0.2650	2.2438	0.9018
HDFC – Growth Fund (G)	2011-12	6.02	-0.4565	-0.0903	-0.0471	-0.0570
	2010-11	11.70	0.8630	0.7275	0.1273	1.0874
	2009-10	4.30	7.8957	0.6541	0.0932	5.4404
	2008-09	-3.46	-4.8585	-3.8655	-0.3226	-3.2102
	2007-08	3.90	-1.1235	2.9022	3.1458	4.3407
	2006-07	-0.39	-0.5380	-0.2522	2.8150	0.9655
	2005-06	-2.93	-11.1691	-3.8047	-2.7207	-0.8513
	2004-05	-4.20	-0.3708	-1.0147	5.5623	0.6904
	2003-04	3.19	6.6730	0.5087	0.5599	6.4143
	2002-03	-2.82	-2.0996	-1.1293	0.1571	-0.7737
	Overall	1.53	-0.5184	-0.5364	0.9370	1.4047

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

A sneak peak at the Sharpe Index, for the funds both HDFC Equity and HDFC Growth suggests the fact that investors are poised and prepared to hug this fund owing to overall positive value for the decade. The positive value is well endorsed in Treynor index as well for HDFC Equity Fund, however, HDFC Growth fund has overall negative Treynor value. The positive alpha for HDFC Equity fund will give the impression of undervalued fund, however, the deterrent of Jensen's alpha is one cannot apply this for long term performance or performance greater than one year. On the other side of the spectrum negative Jensen's alpha for HDFC Growth fund will lead to over valuation of the fund. The overall positive Fama for both the funds has shown the superlative selectivity skills of the fund manager.

The overall M^2 value for HDFC growth fund is superior.

ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF THE FUNDS

HDFC EQUITY FUND

In 16 years, HDFC Equity has underperformed its category just twice. Though one of the sturdiest, the fund does have its moments where investors are confounded, for example, the year

2011. Despite holding up pretty well during the 2008 downturn, its fall this time was higher than that of the average. The comparatively lower exposure to FMCG could be the culprit. This comes after a great run in 2009 and 2010. Going back in time, the returns were pretty muted during the heady days of 2006 and 2007 after an impressive 2005.

The inherent character of the fund enables it to make a strong comeback. The fund manager focuses on quality companies that are reasonably valued with a growth bias. Richly valued investments are not necessarily pursued even if the short-term returns are lucrative. He follows his conviction and focuses on value, not the direction of price movement. That is why the portfolio does not necessarily have momentum stocks or cyclicals. So when the latter are on a run, the fund manager gets punished for his stance.

Being almost fully invested during the doom and gloom period of the first quarter of 2009 paid off handsomely. The market began its upward journey in March and the fund capitalized on this move and thrashed the competition with a 106 per cent return (category average: 83%). In 2010 again it was third best fund in its category.

From 1996 right till 2008, HDFC Equity fell into the “Equity: Large & Mid Cap” category. It was only from 2009 onwards it got categorized into the “Equity: Multi Cap” category. More recently it has been increasing its large-cap allocation.

There’s no denying the impressive track record. In its history of 16 years, the fund has underperformed its category just twice. Not surprisingly, its assets have surged to make it the biggest fund in the category and the second largest open-ended equity fund (December 2011) which resulted in a much more diversified portfolio from what it was in 2008 though the allocation to the top five holdings hovers around 27% and is in line with the category average. The rising asset base has resulted in the expenses being among the lowest in the category, currently at 1.78%

HDFC GROWTH FUND - (G)

The scheme underperforms the Sensex over all time periods Outperforms the category average over most of the time periods.

Background: The sponsor of the HDFC Mutual Fund is Housing Development Finance Corporation Limited (HDFC), which was incorporated in 1977 as the first specialised housing finance institution in India. HDFC AMC was incorporated on 10 December 1999, and today manages average assets worth ₹. 8987874.71 lakhs (as at 31st March 2012).

HDFC Growth Fund - (G) is an open-ended equity-diversified scheme launched in July 2000. It aims to generate long term capital appreciation from a portfolio that is invested predominantly in equity and equity related instruments. The minimum investment amount is Rs 5000, and in multiples of Rs 1000 thereafter. The scheme charges no entry load and 1% for redemption within one year. The unit NAV of the scheme as at 07 September 2012 was ₹.253.882.

Portfolio: The net assets of the scheme increased by Rs 13.19 crore to Rs 352.53 crore in April 2006. The scheme took fresh exposure to four stocks in April 2006 as it purchased 3.79 lakh units (2.87%) of Solar Explosives, 1.00 lakh units (2.13%) of Satyam Computer Services, 50,000 units (1.32%) of Tata Motors and 16,178 units (0.86%) of Divis Laboratories, among others.

The scheme exited from National Aluminium Company by selling 2.75 lakh units (2.38%) and Reliance Communication Ventures by disposing off 1.75 lakh units (1.59%).

Sector wise, the scheme purchased Automobiles-LCVs/HCVs at 2.77%, Pharmaceuticals-Indian-Bulk Drugs at 0.86% and Tyres at 0.83% in April 2006. The scheme exited from Aluminum and Aluminum products at 2.38% in April 2006. The top holdings of the scheme constituted of Petroleum, Gas & Petrochemical products (16.47%), followed by Banks (15.07%) and Software and Consultancy Services (10.45%) among others in March 2012.

It reduced exposure to Bharati Airtel to 1.73% in Telecom, the beleaguered sector. Other which went under 2% are (Crompton Greaves – 1.59%, Tata Chemicals – 1.57%, & IL & FS Transport – 1.48% among others in March 2012.

Performance: The scheme has outperformed the category average over all time periods except over one year. It underperformed the Sensex over all time periods. Over the three-month period ended 17 May 2006, the scheme posted 17.85% returns outperforming the category average of 13.61%. During the same period, the scheme underperformed the Sensex, which posted 79.69% returns.

Since inception, the scheme posted 328.46% returns outperforming the category average of 236.12%.

CONCLUSIONS

Leaving, the common caveats attached to the mutual funds aside, HDFC mutual funds occupy the top notch in the industry, this can be due to superlative performance coupled with strong governance structure or the superlative skills of the fund manager. Having said this, it would be pertinent to mention that we cannot leave the rest of the funds in isolation unless one is completely tilted towards HDFC, due to sheer affinity.

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